

Speculation on Relation Between Special Relativity, Newtonian Mechanics and Simple Quantum Mechanics

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Historically, special relativity followed as a generalization of Newtonian mechanics and later quantum mechanics (both nonrelativistic and relativistic) was developed as a somewhat independent theory with some connections to Newtonian/special relativistic concepts such as energy and momentum and their conservation. For example, the Newtonian concept of a potential $V(x)$ is used in quantum mechanics.

Here we wish to consider the notion of a system seen from different frames moving with constant speed ($-v$) together with some basic physical ideas that are presumed to hold at any scale such as the idea of a push or pull changing the speed of a particle and the notion of speed itself. We argue that one may develop special relativistic equations in such a manner, but at the same time consider notions of dp/dt and dE/dx linked not only to Newtonian mechanical ideas, but at the same time to quantum mechanics, by generalizing these forms.

We argue that one may start with the notion of energy, momentum and their conservation together with the generalizations of a linear force linked to finite $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$. This allows one to a priori write, based on conservation of energy for $v \ll c$: $\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \} + G(x) = E$ ((1)). Here E is total energy which is constant at each x and $G(x)$ is some pre-existing function representing energy which is not motion energy. Now, an object at rest with rest mass m_0 transforms to E, p , but this E is a combination of motion and rest mass. Thus, not all energy is associated with motion, as there is energy in a rest mass. Similarly, a compressed spring presumably has energy (if one believes in energy conservation) even though there is no translation occurring. Thus, $G(x)$ represents a physical system linked with fixed energy in x (which is not translation energy) as well as delivering momentum hits. We argue that ((1)) is a general statement which requires no knowledge of Newtonian mechanics and may be written a priori.

The problem with ((1)) is that it contains two sets of unknowns, $\{ a(p) \}$ and $G(x)$. If one knew one, one could find the other. Now one may write $\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \}$ as $.5m_0 \ v_{rms}(x) \ v_{rms}(x)$ and if $dx = \hbar / (m_0 \ v_{rms}(x))$ is small compared to what one considers to be a tiny dx (based on the system length), then one could very well consider a particle as moving with constant $v_{rms}(x)$ within dx . This would then lead to a Newtonian picture if one could measure such a situation experimentally. It turns out that one can because this is in fact what one measures on classical scales. Thus, one may find $V(x)$ in a classical regime and then use $V(x) = G(x)$ to solve the quantum bound problem.

The formalism we suggest completely links special relativity, quantum mechanics (simple aspects) and Newtonian mechanics.

Special Relativity with No Newtonian Mechanics

We wish to consider special relativity (i.e. the notion of particles seen from frames moving at different constant $-v$ speeds) with no notion of Newtonian mechanics. We do, however, assume that one knows some basic physical ideas, i.e.

((2)) There is a notion of constant speed given by $v = x/t$

((3)) A particle moving with one speed (even 0) can change this speed if given a hit (push or pull). We consider speed in one dimension here.

((4)) A particle at rest is linked with a push or pull because it requires an initial force to move it. This is Newton's idea of inertia (a physical observation) and we assign a number m_0 (rest mass) to account for it.

Given only the idea of spacetime x, t and $x=vt$ for constant speed, a particle at rest at $x=0, t$ will be seen to be moving from a frame moving at $-v$. The person in the moving frame assumes that the particle was once at $x'=0, t=0$ (where we use ' to specify x' and t' in the moving frame just in case they differ from the rest frame). Then:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((4))$$

In the rest frame, however, one has $x=0, t$ ((5)) and so x, t and x', t' are not the same and one needs a transformation to link them.

We note that at this point we have a vector r (although we use the simple one dimensional x) and a number t . One may suggest a transformation of the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ t' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g(v) & v g(v) \\ v g(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ t \end{bmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

This still leaves $g(v)$ unknown.

We suggest that there is another number in the picture, namely Newton's inertia (linked to force). We suggest that it may be associated with a vector p if seen from a moving frame because a moving object can break a window (example) and so not only is m_0 linked with force, but this p proportional to v as well. We suggest that ((5)) should also apply to $(p=0, m_0 c c)$. Here c is a fixed constant for unit purposes.

Then $(p=0, m_0 c c)$ transforms to (pc, E) . The rest frame and what is seen in the moving frame represent the same physical system and so one might argue that one must mathematically show this equivalence. The usual way is to use a modulus from the transformation matrix ((5)). As argued in previous notes:

$$EE + pcpc = momoccc \quad ((6))$$

Cannot hold because one physically assumes that $E > m_0 c c$ as it requires effort (or work) to move $m_0 c c$ and this should be manifest. If this is the case, then one requires:

$$-EE + pccp = -momoccc \quad ((7))$$

This leads to:

$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ ((8)) and one may use ((5)) explicitly.

This is all well-known, but physically a particle changes speed because it receives a hit (push or pull which Newton called force). As a result, an $m_0 c^2$ at rest must receive a hit in order to change to a dp (if one uses dv instead of v).

Given ((8)), one may write the Lorentz invariant:

$$-E(dv)' + dp x' c = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((9))$$

If one assumes that $dv \ll c$ (which it must be if c is the speed of light, i.e. a maximum speed as seen from ((8))), then

$$t' = t$$

Then: $-dE t' + dp dx' c = 0$ ((10)) Here we use dx' for x' as dv is involved and $x=0$ initially

If one has $t=dt$ and divides by $dt dx'$ (where $t'=dt'$), then

$$-dE/dx' + dp/dt' = 0 \quad ((11))$$

If one considers the $dv \ll c$ limit, $p = m_0 v$ and $E = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$ ((12))

Note: We do not call ((12)) Newtonian mechanics, we only suggest that it represents the situation for $v \ll c$, where $v = dv$.

Now, $dp/dt' = m_0 dv \text{ particle} / dt'$ for m_0 constant. Physically this should be associated with a hit (i.e. a push or pull or force because that is what changes the speed of the particle.)

Then dE/dx' and dp/dt' both represent the same force. This brings about a main point. Even though dE/dx' and dp/dt' look like derivatives in ((11)), they are not. One actually has finite dt' and dx' , even though dv is very small.

We thus suggest that one has the notion of E and p ((8)) as well as the idea of a force changing these which is linked to finite dx' and dt' . If these values are finite, however, is there perhaps a limiting value? ((11)) does not show such a limiting value as it deals with dE and dp and dE is really the change in energy due to a dv , whereas $E = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$ describes the total energy (which is linked to the full idea of inertia).

We thus suggest one should be able to consider v instead of simply dv . In such a case, it seems that natural dx' and dt' values appear, i.e.

$$-Et + pcx = -m_0 c^2 t_1 \quad ((13))$$

For a given x, t on the trajectory $x = vt$, $x + \hbar/p$ and $t + \hbar/E$ yield the same LHS value and $t + \hbar/m_0 c^2$ the same RHS value if $p=0$ is linked with $x + \hbar/p$ ($p=0$).

This gives rise to finite dx and dt values, but we argue that a change of p in $dt = \hbar/E$ (a linear average approach) indicates how a hit (force) is delivered. If one calculates the value of dt, it will be very tiny in terms of values in the classical world. (Note: \hbar appears due to photon considerations which we have discussed in other notes and do not repeat here.)

We suggest that ((13)) means that the concept of E and p (which we call energy of a free particle based on rest mass and movement and the vector momentum) exist. Furthermore, minimal values for dx' and dt' also exist based on \hbar/p and \hbar/E and we link these to changes needed to exert a force to create E, p on average.

We then suggest that there exist t and x values within dt' and dx' and that the force linked with E and p may be delivered at any of these points without preference, i.e. one has a probabilistic situation. If one considers that E and p are conserved, then the probability should have the form:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((14))$$

If it is to be Lorentz invariant and conserve E and p in a product probability for the same x,t. A complex $\exp(i\theta)$ is used because there is no real weight difference for any free particle.

We now have the notion of energy, momentum, their conservation and a probability ((14)).

Conservation of Energy Requirements

Let us consider a particle, linked with probability ((14)) which undergoes various stochastic hits in a region of space such that it is localized and energy is conserved. It is known that energy is:

$E = m_0c^2/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, but in the nonrelativistic case one may consider $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ as changing in x.

Given that ((14)) is a probability, one should formally write:

$$\text{Motion energy in } x \text{ (called kinetic energy)} = \frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)} \quad ((15))$$

Here we use the nonrelativistic limit. There is still no notion of Newtonian mechanics. A completely a priori conservation of energy in space equation would be:

$$\frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)} + G(x) = E \quad ((16))$$

Here E is some fixed total energy and G(x) some fixed energy in x function. This gives rise to the idea of stored energy in a system. It is not the case that all energy is in motion. We argued above that m_0c^2 is linked with inertia force and it then becomes E and so m_0c^2 is no motional energy. One may further postulate stored energy in a compressed spring. G(x) should be like this compressed spring energy and be associated with a very large object that essentially has 0 kinetic energy during an interaction.

The problem is that there are two unknowns in ((16)), the set $\{a(p)\}$ and $G(x)$. In order to alleviate the problems, one may consider

$$\left\{ \sum_p a(p) p p / 2m \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} = .5 m_0 v_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x) \quad ((17))$$

If $\hbar / (m_0 v_{rms}(x)) \ll dx$, where dx is taken to be a small length relative to the overall system length, then it seems that one could replace the LHS of ((18)) with a single speed $v_{rms}(x)$. One is then led to the notion of Newtonian mechanics, i.e.

$$.5 m_0 v_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x) + G(x) = E \quad ((17))$$

Before this point, we had nonrelativistic quantum mechanics. ((17)) is an equation which may be measured in a classical world scale experiment because one may measure $v_{rms}(x)$ in a small dx interval and then find $G(x)$. This $G(x)$ may be called $V(x)$ and then be used in ((16)) to find the set $\{a(p)\}$.

Thus, Newtonian mechanics emerges at the last step as a means of solving for $G(x)$ in the situation $\hbar / (m_0 v_{rms}(x)) \ll dx$.

We suggest that this picture links special relativity, basic physical observation, quantum mechanics (simple aspects) and Newtonian mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one does not need $F=dp/dt$ or any specific Newtonian mechanical equation to derive special relativity, i.e. the consideration of a particle as seen in a rest frame and one moving with $-v$. We do suggest that one requires some basic physical notions (which Newton already considered). In particular, one needs $x=vt$ and the idea that a particle at rest has Newtonian inertia, i.e. requires a force to move it. This means that there is a number, m_0 (rest mass), which measures force associated with a rest object. When seen from a moving frame, there is a number E and a vector $p = E/cv$ which are both linked to force because p , the vector is linked with the breaking or impact on a target. If one considers $E > m_0 c^2$, one is led to: $-E^2 + p^2 c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4$ and can find $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ in the transformation ((5)). As a result, one has the notion of E energy linked to inertia m_0 and motion and a momentum p , but nothing else. We further suggest that energy is not only linked to inertia and movement, but may also be associated with stored energy as in a compressed spring. We also suggest conservation for all kinds of energy and momentum and note that one may take the $v \ll c$ limit of relativistic expressions for E and p . At this point, there is no Newton's second law, or quantum mechanics.

We also note that a push or pull is required to change a p or E . If one considers a frame which moves with $-dv$, then one may obtain $-dE'/dx' + dp/dt' = 0$ and argue that each term represents force. This force, however, is associated with changes to E due to motion. We suggest introducing a more general idea, namely E'/dx' and p/dt' which describes a kind of linear average force which balances i.e. $-E' dt' + p' dx' = 0$. This then gives rise to finite dt' and dx' values, i.e. \hbar/E and \hbar/p . We suggest that E' or p' act within these finite values as they are associated with force, but may actually strike at any x' or t' within dx' and dt' . This leads to a

probabilistic picture with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as the probability. At this point there are no Newtonian equations. We further note that this probability enforces the $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$. In other words, they are manifest in nature. This helps to explain why a probability should exist in the first place if one is not convinced by the argument of a stochastic force.

If one believes that energy is conserved then ((16)) should hold, but to find a function $G(x)$ (really potential $V(x)$) which holds energy, one must do an experiment and this is most conveniently done in a scale in which $\hbar/(m v_{rms}(x)) < dx =$ small unit relative to the overall system size. One may then find $G(x)=V(x)$ experimentally in this Newtonian nonrelativistic region and because motion energy follows from special relativity, this also applies to nonrelativistic quantum mechanics. Thus, Newtonian mechanics is based on a scale for which $\hbar/(m v_{rms}(x))$ is tiny compared to a dx in the system. Otherwise, one is dealing with the more general quantum mechanical case.